

ECOTOURISM'S DETRIMENTAL IMPACTS ON WILDLIFE

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Abstract: *Ecotourism is considered a tool for wildlife conservation and world countries hope that ecotourism activities will increase income for local communities and make them value wildlife more. However, protecting wildlife is not easy. Though many countries have created national parks and conducted law enforcement there is still a threat for wildlife as many people rely on hunting for making a living. Tourists' visitation to natural areas may have significant impacts on wildlife therein. Wild animals usually have an evasive response to human activities and these activities can affect to their health and living condition. In most cases the behavior of wild animals can change in the presence of people. This might have long-term negative consequences not only to wildlife population but also to the entire ecological communities. It can be challenging to explore all these impacts over long periods due to the multitude of interacting factors.*

Keywords: *ecotourism, wildlife habitats, biodiversity preservation, conservation, environmental education*

Introduction

Background information

Tourism approaches are aimed at eliminating negative impacts on the environment and introducing benefits to local communities. For these reasons, different alternative tours are being supported by people. Among them, ecotourism stands out for its advanced conservation goals and improved livelihood of locals (Stronza and Durham, 2008). Even if ecotourism could offer high economic benefit, there would have been direct industry impact that causes more harm than benefit. These include altering habitat for tourism practices, cutting trails, and disturbing wild animals (Butynski and Kalina, 1998). The diseases transmitted to wildlife or some changes in their health by disturbance of daily routines or high-stress levels were discovered by biologists (Isaacs, 2000; Ananthaswamy, 2004). When Javier Gordillo and his colleagues (1983) studied the Cofan case they came to the decision that ecotourism can both deliver benefits to local people and local ecosystems while also can present new social and ecological challenges.

Natural resource agencies can be susceptible to unproductive political behavior. Local resources will be used in pursuing funds in the political arena (Shabman, 1995). They also may take part in projects that can increase revenues, however, do not produce amenities they are designed to provide (Bhagwati, 1982). For example, refuge might look for funding

for a politically attractive visitors' center and establish a new road for recreational vehicular traffic at the expense of more important projects, like removing unique and exotic species.

Regulations that set up to project wildlife resources are expensive, and uncertain in their effectiveness (Baumol and Oates, 1998). Public awareness of wild animal species in certain areas might complicate wildlife management ability to control specific animal populations when tourists help to protect certain attractive, but troublesome species, for instance, white-tailed deer (Morrow, 1998). Ecotourism can be an essential tool for persuading tourist service entrepreneurs to limit creating problems for wildlife habitats in the name of self-interest. Some tourists can pay more for an untouched and clean environment. Protected natural areas can include untouched nature the main areas of wildlife conservation and a tourist destination platform. But people are negatively affecting most surrounding territories, destroying unique habitats, hunting both legally and illegally spreading diseases. Carnivores and herbivores are under noticeable threat because of poaching and trophy hunting on the borders of nature reserves (Svetlana et al., 2021).

Literature Review

Impact of ecotourism activities on wildlife

Ecotourism practices have been continuously increasing and are still constituting threat to endangered animals. The negative affect of these popular activities on wildlife is difficult to predict because of space and time, and actual effects still poorly understood (Knight, 2009). Manor and Saltz (2003) stated that repeated flushing events of resting wildlife by people practicing ecotourism activities put stress on them, and these effects will undoubtedly may lead to a reduction of local population distribution if not species abundance.

Ecotourism is widely known as a means of commercial profit, community development and environmental conservation and all these can be achieved (Buckley, 2016). However, it can produce environmental problems. Ecotourism may not all the time follow conservation objectives of land protection. For instance, recreational activities correlate with species decrease that causes wildlife to flee (Sutherland, 2007). According to the studies of Wheeler (2013) development of ecotourism the progressive abandonment of traditional farming practices including cattle grazing may further reduce richness and attractiveness of these habitats because of heterogeneity and patchiness of the landscape.

For conservation planners and land managers protecting biodiversity and wildlife from potential negative impacts should be the main concern. Ecotourism can create threats to the population growth and development of the protected area. Disturbance can affect both biodiversity and wildlife which cannot be measured as distinct impacts (McKinney, 2014). Almost all animal species are sensitive to recreational activities (Andersen et al., 2012), but not to disturbance (McKinney, 2014). Measuring sensitivity is difficult, and results may vary depending on populations, physical environment, and period of time.

Methodology

For the research process, secondary data have been used. With the advance of modern technology, it was accessible to collect a vast amount of data for the research. As secondary data can provide utilization in several ways it has given the chance of collecting and

evaluating steps. Scientific journals and different sites have been collected to have better results. Downloaded papers by researchers and data from journals present challenges that wild animals are coming across because of ecotourism activities (Table1). Here effect sizes together for common categories have been grouped and average effect sizes for each category have been calculated.

Table1

Negative influence of human activities on wildlife

Method of assessment Avoidance responses Time budgets Physiological responses

Negative valence Antipredator responses

*longer FID, huge fleeing population, longer alert distance, escape behavior, greater escape speed, longer distance fled, longer latency to return *increased body movement, locomotion/vigilance, aggression, comfort grooming, sparring, *increased heart rate, greater plasma glucocorticoid, concentrations, increased metabolic rate

*shorter distance to cover maintained, decreased duration of encounter, reduced residency, avoidance of a particular area, reduced percent daytime activity, greater depth of activity *foraging, feeding, inactive resting, social behavior, nursing, attending

*mineral imbalance, more injuries, slower wound healing, greater parasite, slower growth rate, reduced nest success, smaller body

Source from: Philip W. Bateman “Biological Conservation”, 2017

Table 2

Human actions and animal reactions in Galapagos Marine Reserve

Human actions Animal reactions

Category	Action	Category	Reaction
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Persecution	Visitors move directly toward the animal	Evasion	Change in direction withdrawing from the visitors or leaving the area
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Use of flash	Use of flash to photograph an animal	Alert	Interruption in the behavior observed when first encountered followed by the animal directing its attention to its visitor
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Abrupt movement	Sudden movement of extremity or the torso by the visitor nearest to the observed animal	Approach	Voluntarily approaches the visitors
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Noise	Knocking the tank, use of alert signal bells, shouting, laughing, speaking loudly	None	No change in behavior or direction of movement is observed
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Simple presence	None of the above occur, the visitor only observes
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Source from: Priscilla Cubero-Pardo “The impact of ecotourism on wild animals”, 2007

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Negative valence	Antipredator responses *longer FID, huge fleeing population, longer alert distance, escape behavior, greater escape speed, longer distance fled, longer latency to return	*increased body movement, locomotion/vigilance, aggression, comfort grooming, sparring,	*increased heart rate, greater plasma glucocorticoid, concentrations, increased metabolic rate
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Results

Avoidance responses are usually considered as measures of the effects of tourist activities. Quick avoidance measures present outcomes that are interpreted as having positive valence with animals exposed to tourist activities letting an approaching person come closer before moving away. Time budget data indicated different impacts of tourist activities. Generally, animals spend less time immobile in the presence of tourists, but other time budget measures should be both positive and negative valence behavior. Physiological measures showed overall negative effects of measures of tourist activities.

Snorkeling was the most reaction evasive human activity for animals. Animals immediately responded to the flash photography with evasive reactions, some even completely left the area. Animals paid attention to the noise made by visitors. No reaction was noticed when they remained quiet.

Conclusion

Human visitation to natural areas may have noticeable effects on the environment and wildlife of the area. Ecotourism is not always a benign activity with low disturbance, but it can have big implications for the reproductive success, long-term viability of unique species. Tourists also can directly impact. They can cause mortality by providing artificial food recourses. They can contribute to habitat degradation. Undoubtedly, tourism is a major tool in the economy, however, potential negative impacts caused by human activities should be understood.

Environmental education is as important as ecotourism and equally important in conservation projects. Special attention should be paid to visitor behavior. Stresses on animals because of ecotourism activities may result in changes in species composition, community structure, and population density. Developing management strategies in national parks can be another good method to minimize detrimental impacts.

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